

Recommended citation: Oâ■Mahony, T., Hill, M., Canty, N., Rea, J., McShera, S., Hamilton, D., & Murray, M. (2020). Reflecting on a Learning Community in Engineering: Impact on Individuals and Their Teaching. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 366-375). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14653835.

REFLECTING ON A LEARNING COMMUNITY IN ENGINEERING: IMPACT ON INDIVIDUALS AND THEIR TEACHING

T. O'Mahony¹, M. Hill, N. Canty, D. Hamilton, J. Rea, S. McShera and M. Murray
Cork Institute of Technology
Cork, Ireland

Conference Key Areas: *Niche & Novel*

Keywords: *Professional Development, Learning Community, Qualitative Research, Programme Development*

ABSTRACT

In this contribution, the authors who are all members of the same Learning Community, collaborated to explore the impact of that learning community one year after its formation. We are especially keen to determine the impact, if any, that the learning community has had on our programmes and teaching practice. Given the small group that is involved and the subjective nature of the topic, we have selected a qualitative approach to evaluate impact. The data collected involved a set of documents, module descriptors, produced by the group over the past year and a narrative response to series of open-ended questions. The limitation of the narrative response is that it reveals participants subjective view of the impact of the learning community on their own professional development. The role of the document analysis is to ascertain whether these beliefs translated into action and whether participants modified the modules that they teach via our formal module descriptor document. The results identify that participation in the Learning Community resulted in a significant impact on programme development. Specifically, while participants only represent 39% of the teaching staff within the Department, they contributed over 70% of the changes to module learning outcomes that focused on important graduate attributes and without this contribution the Department would have been unable to transform programmes to the desired extent. Overall then, the learning community was impactful for this group of staff, but the impact on student learning has yet to be established.

¹ Corresponding Author
tom.omahony@cit.ie

1 INTRODUCTION

Higher education is experiencing unprecedented changes as a result of its massification, increasingly diverse student body, funding challenges, changed conceptions of what it means to learn, greater expectations around quality and accountability from various stakeholders and expectations of “value for money” from those that pay. As a response to some of these expectations and demands, nations and institutions have turned to the professional development of those that teach within higher education settings. While traditional approaches such as seminars and workshops are widely used, other approaches such as Learning Communities would appear to be under-utilised. Moreover, there is much uncertainty regarding the effectiveness of different approaches. In this paper, we discuss the potential of Learning Communities as an effective means of professional development and evaluate the impact of a Learning Community which we are all currently participating in.

2 PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION

2.1 Evidence of impact & high impact professional development

Professional development within higher education general seeks to have an impact on teacher's *ways of thinking* or *ways of acting* and a consequential effect on students learning. Within higher education, *ways of thinking* is often associated with the constructivist philosophy [1] while desirable *ways of acting* are aligned with student or learner-centred teaching strategies [2]. A general, desirable impact on student learning is to encourage a deep approach to learning or to foster understanding [3] while specific impacts focus on measuring changes in learning outcomes. Within the educational literature, traditional forms of teacher professional development such as seminars, workshops and conferences are heavily criticised because there is little evidence that they result in these impacts on teachers or students [4]. This limited impact, it is argued, is largely due to the nature of these events which are short-term and sporadic in time and encourage teachers to be largely passive. In contrast, features of high-quality (impactful) professional development activities involve actively engaging teachers, over a sustained duration and involve a number of teachers from the same school or department [5]. The review compiled by [5] also suggests that professional development activity that focuses on the discipline and ways of teaching and learning within that discipline, and activities that are coherent with local or national policies are more likely to be impactful. In their review of instructional development in higher education, [6] also found evidence that instructional development interventions which extend over time are more impactful compared with one-time events and that more-traditional formats (seminars, workshops, short courses, etc) had less impact than alternative formats (e.g. peer learning). In related work, [7] characterised and explored the strategies that are used to promote change in undergraduate instructional practices in STEM courses. Their review identified that effective strategies involve long-term interventions; seeks to change the beliefs of the individuals involved; and recognises

a college or university as a complex system and that effective strategies are compatible with this system [7].

2.2 Learning communities definition and types

A faculty or academic learning community is a special type of community of practice that originated in the USA at Miami University in the late 1970s. A Learning Community has been defined as “a cross-disciplinary community of 8-12 faculty (and, sometimes, professional staff and graduate students) engaged in an active, collaborative, yearlong curriculum focused on enhancing and assessing undergraduate learning with frequent activities that promote learning, development, SoTL, and community” [8]. Learning communities are often categorised as cohort-based if the community is drawn from a specific category of staff e.g. part-time staff or early-career staff or topic-based if the community was formed to address or enhance a particular issue or opportunity e.g. learning technology. Participation is voluntary and often accompanied by some incentive e.g. a grant that can be used for teaching or research purposes. [9] provides good examples of a variety of engineering learning communities including topic-based ones that focused on the flipped classroom and cohort-based ones that supported first-year faculty. Another good example is the eight-month long topic-based faculty learning community, reported in [10], who’s goal was to increase both persistence and performance of under-represented students (e.g. females) in key STEM courses.

Table 1. Learning Communities as Effective forms of Professional Development

For professional development to be impactful it should	Specific characteristics of Learning Communities.
extend over time, [5]–[7]	They exist for a semester, year or longer
involve active participation, [5] [6]	Individuals are expected to engage in some specific project
involve community participation [5]	Involve 6 – 12 participants
be discipline-specific [5]	Are often discipline-based
take into account the complexity of the social context, [5], [7]	Often are local and informal in nature

Table 1 compares specific characteristics of faculty learning communities with features of impactful professional development as identified by [5]–[7] and from this comparison it is evident that faculty learning communities have the potential to impact on teaching and learning in a significant way. Some studies have evidenced this. The largest such study to date, [8] reported that this type of professional development resulted in changes in teachers beliefs and attitudes about teaching as well as improvements in student learning. However, this data was collected using a self-reported questionnaire and there was no direct measure of staff or student

learning. Studies that adopted a more rigorous evaluation support these findings, though these studies tend to be very small in nature. In [10] the authors report that 23 of the 27 projects (85%) analyzed produced “small and measurable” results, which was defined as achieving at least a 2% increase in grades, retention, improved attitudes, or STEM interest. More than half of the projects (67%) resulted in a 5% or greater increase in one or more of these measures. In a study that focused on enhancing Latino student success, participants reported increased awareness and understanding of teaching, learning and advising a culturally diverse student body as well as reporting changes to courses and assignments to make both more inclusive [11]. While this data was gathered from self-reported questionnaires, the open-ended nature of the data provided opportunities for participants to provide examples to justify or illustrate impact.

2.3 Contribution of this paper

While attempts to evaluate the impact of professional development have been ongoing for a long time, much of this evaluation is heavily criticised as only relying on self-reports from participants [6]. For example, [7] report that only “only 21% of articles that studied implementation of a change strategy were categorized as presenting strong evidence to support claims of success or failure of the strategy”. The potential problem with this self-reported data is aptly illustrated in a study reported by [12] which showed a clear disconnect between faculty’s perceptions of their teaching (documented through a self-reported questionnaire) and their actual practices (documented through an analysis of recordings of actual practice). Hence the professional development discourse has argued for more rigorous and varied approaches to evaluate the impact of these activities within higher education settings. Given the small group that is involved and the subjective nature of the topic, we have adopted a qualitative approach to evaluate impact. Our primary data is a set of documents, module descriptors, produced by the group over the past year. These documents were then analysed to identify changes to those module descriptors that arose as a result of participating in the learning community. As these are formally approved course descriptions they document either actualized or planned changes to modules and hence represent much stronger evidence than simple self-reported questionnaire data. This analysis is then used to evidence the impact that the learning community has had on our Department to date.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Question

Following on from the literature review of the previous section, the specific research question explored was whether participation in a topic-based engineering learning community had an impact on the Department (programmes and individual staff) and to assess the extent of that impact.

3.2 Research Method

This research adopted a mixed methods approach which is consistent with the pragmatic research question posed [13]. The primary research method is a content

analysis of existing documents. These documents are the formal *module descriptors* that are used to define the courses that comprise programmes within our institution. Significant changes to these imply changes to teaching, learning or assessment activity within those modules. We elected to focus on analysing changes to module learning outcomes, as these represent the most significant part of these documents. Hence the analysis consisted of counting the number of module learning outcomes that changed over this period, categorising the nature of this change and identifying whether the change originated from a participant of the learning community or otherwise. This analysis intends to capture significant changes to teaching practices by participants of the learning community relative to others in the department. This data was then supported by reflections from individual participants of the learning community. These reflections were in response to three open-ended questions and were thematically analysed. Convergence of findings lends a certain confidence to the findings and adds to the validity and reliability of the research [13]

3.3 Participants

In January 2019, the Teaching and Learning Unit launched an initiative to support and recognise Learning Communities within our institute. The authors responded to this initiative and in February we were informed that our application was successful and that we were formally recognised as one of 13 Learning Communities within the institute. The stated objectives of our Learning Community are to *1) to enhance the programmes that we teach on by considering how key graduate competencies e.g. writing, teamwork can be integrated throughout those programmes; 2) to support the professional development of staff; 3) to research our teaching practice*. Eight staff members were involved in the original application, one has since left the Department. Our Department has 18 full-time academic staff with predominantly teaching roles so this Learning Community represents 39% of the academic teaching staff within our Department. To date we have typically met for one hour every second week over the course of each semester. During the first year, the focus of activity was to plan a revised curriculum that would achieve the first objective. As a starting point we focused on three key graduate competences – writing, teamwork and ethical responsibility – as collectively we felt that our existing programmes did not develop these competencies as well as they could or should. Rather than create specific writing, teamwork or ethics modules, our approach was to integrate those skills and attributes into existing technical modules across the programme from first to fourth year. This approach mirrors that advocated by the CDIO initiative [14]. This semester our focus shifted to how we might implement or realise some of those planned changes, various strategies were being piloted and participants were encouraged and supported to consider documenting and researching some of this activity. However, COVID19 interrupted much of this planned work as the institute was formally closed mid-way through our teaching semester.

3.4 Data Collection

The primary data collected consists of a set of module descriptors for two four year programmes that this Department is responsible for – a B.Eng (Hons) in Electrical Engineering and a B.Eng. (Hons) in Electronic Engineering. Each programme consists of eight semesters. On average six, five ECTS credit modules form each semester so, on average, each programme consists of 48 modules. Some modules are serviced in from other Departments e.g. the Department of Mathematics and those modules were not considered in this analysis. The majority of currently approved modules were validated in 2015 and are publically available (<https://courses.cit.ie/>). Both programmes are currently being reviewed with all modules having being revised or updated and are currently being submitted for approval to the central unit responsible for Academic Quality. Hence the data that was collected consisted of 88 currently approved modules and the 82 revised modules (some elective modules were removed as part of the review). These were then compared to identify changes, and analysed to categorise the nature of that change. To complement this, participants contributed to an on-line text and were asked to respond to three open ended questions. These questions are presented in Appendix I.

3.5 Data Analysis

Module descriptors were analysed by identifying Learning Outcomes that had changed between the currently approved module descriptors and the revised module descriptors. We focused on Learning Outcomes as these represent significant changes to the module. Within our institution, it is recommended that all module descriptor documents contain between 4 – 6 learning outcomes. Hence a change to one or more of these can represent a substantial change in that module – which would then be reflected in changes to indicative content or assessment practices. Only significant changes to module learning outcomes were considered where “significant” was interpreted to mean a new learning outcome added or that the learning outcome was changed to the extent that new content would need to be included to address it. Minor changes to learning outcomes e.g. revisions to clarify the meaning were not counted and any other changes to the module descriptor document were also not recorded. These significant changes to learning outcomes were counted. They were also categorised as predominantly reflecting a development of content or a development of a graduate attribute. In our view the development of a graduate attribute (e.g. incorporating teamwork) is a more challenging change to realise and is representative of more professional development. This categorisation also helps to directly evidence the impact of this Learning Community. Finally, the changes were also categorised as either originating from one of the seven participants of this Learning Community or from the remaining 11 staff members. Data from the open-ended questionnaires was thematically analysed based on the approach advocated in [15].

4 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Impact on Programme

Tables 2 and 3 summarise the scope of the work while table 4 presents the main results. In table 2 and 3, the column “*no of modules analysed*” represents the number of modules on both of the existing and revised programmes that are taught by staff within our department. This includes both mandatory and elective modules and excludes “service-in” modules e.g. from the Dept. of Mathematics. The total number of learning outcomes (LO’s) is also documented so that the changes recorded in table 4 can be placed in some sort of context. The number of modules analysed in the currently approved programme and revised Electrical Engineering programme are not the same as a 15 credit Work Placement module was added (this is counted as a single module) and a number of elective modules were removed from this programme.

Table 2. Analysis metrics for B.Eng. (Hons) in Electrical Engineering

Currently Approved Programme		Revised Programme	
No of Modules Analysed	Total Number of LO’s Analysed	No of Modules Analysed	Total Number of LO’s Analysed
46	229	40	222

Table 3. Analysis metrics for B.Eng. (Hons) in Electronic Engineering

Currently Approved Programme		Revised Programme	
No of Modules Analysed	Total Number of LO’s Analysed	No of Modules Analysed	Total Number of LO’s Analysed
42	211	42	225

Table 4. Evidence of Impact

B.Eng. (Hons) in	Electronic Engineering	Electrical Engineering
Total number of content focused learning outcomes changed	25	34
Total number of graduate attribute type learning outcomes changed	39	40
% of content-focused learning outcomes from LC participants	28%	44%
% of graduate attribute type learning outcomes from LC participants	62%	83%

Approximately 30% of the learning outcomes of both programmes changed during this current review. Approximately 36% of the discipline-specific content focused learning outcomes were generated by participants from this Learning Community. This

contribution is largely consistent with the size of the Learning Community which represents 39% of the Departments teaching staff. However, participants from this Learning Community contributed over 70% of the learning outcomes that were focused on graduate attributes. In the majority, these learning outcomes related to the development of writing or teamwork skills and ethical attributes. In the context of these important learning outcomes, the Learning Community has punched above its weight. An alternative way of looking at it is, in the absence of this Learning Community, the Department might have only generated ~17 new graduate-attribute type learning outcomes for each programme and largely failed in its objective to enhance both programmes.

4.2 Impact on Individuals

While Table 4 evidences the impact of the Learning Community on the programmes within this Department it could be argued that these revisions largely represent a plan that does not evidence a direct impact on teachers, teaching or learning. Reflections from participants help to support the argument that participating in the Learning Community has had an impact on *how they think* and *how they teach*. For example, one participant discussed how they have been struggling with a module that was particularly heavy with theory and mathematical concepts. The individual commented on how they had re-designed the module, including the assessment strategy to “make the module more project based. The emphasis will be on learning-by-doing, and will hopefully lead to a more enjoyable module and a deeper learning of the topic. I also hope the module will give learners more confidence and foster independent thinking”. A second participant reflected on how, in the past “when trying to improve a module, I focused primarily on *what* was being taught and rarely *how* it was being taught (italics in the original)” but how the Learning Community “discussions really emphasised the importance of engaging the students to really think about the material”. This has resulted in a change of focus with “increased design work – where students must really apply what they’ve learned. I’m delighted with the immediate impact on the students’ understanding – they seem to enjoy it also”. Other, more specific topics that were highlighted were increased use of formative and peer assessment and increased use of technology within the classroom (e.g. audience response systems), outside of the classroom (the learning management system) and to support assessment. More generally, and consistent with much of the existing literature on Learning Communities, participants reflected on the benefits of being able to discuss, explore and share problems and ideas and how the support and encouragement from colleagues enables them to deal with the challenge associated with developing their teaching practices.

5 CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The focus of this article has been to evaluate the impact of a single engineering Learning Community. Recognising the limitations of relying exclusively on self-

reports of impact, here we focused on evaluating the impact that this Learning Community had on programme development within our Department. A review of formal module descriptor documents reveals that Learning Community participants significantly contributed to the changes documented in our recently revised programmes. Specifically, while participants only represent 39% of the teaching staff within the Department, they contributed over 70% of the changes to module learning outcomes that focused on important graduate attributes. Given that the only obvious difference between participants and other staff within the Department is participation in the Learning Community, we tentatively conclude that this effect can be attributed to the Learning Community. Reflections from participants help support this conclusion.

This article helps to support the argument that Learning Communities can be a really effective mechanism for professional development within higher education. A direct implication then is that more higher education institutions should consider fostering and supporting Learning Communities to a greater extent than they currently do. A limitation of this research is its small-scale and particular focus – which makes it difficult to generalise findings. However, the findings are broadly consistent with existing research on Learning Communities. A second limitation is that, to date, we don't have evidence of a direct impact on student learning. Future work intends redress this limitation by documenting and reporting the impact that the revised programmes have had on student learning.

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the Teaching and Learning Unit at Cork Institute of Technology which funded this research via the *Learning Communities Initiative*.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. A. Ertmer and T. J. Newby, "Behaviorism, cognitivism, constructivism: Comparing critical features from an instructional design perspective," *Perform. Improv. Q.*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 43–71, 2013, doi: 10.1002/piq.
- [2] M. Weimer, *Learner-centered teaching : five key changes to practice*, 2nd ed. Jossey-Bass, 2013.
- [3] N. Entwistle, *Teaching for Understanding at University. Deep Approaches and Distinctive Ways of Thinking*. Palgrave Macmillan, 2009.
- [4] L. Darling-Hammond, "Teacher education and the American future," *J. Teach. Educ.*, vol. 61, no. 1–2, pp. 35–47, 2010, doi: 10.1177/0022487109348024.
- [5] L. M. Desimone, "Improving impact studies of teachers' professional development: Toward better conceptualizations and measures," *Educ. Res.*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 181–199, 2009, doi: 10.3102/0013189X08331140.
- [6] A. Stes, M. Min-Leliveld, D. Gijbels, and P. Van Petegem, "The impact of instructional development in higher education: The state-of-the-art of the research," *Educ. Res. Rev.*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 25–49, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.edurev.2009.07.001.

- [7] C. Henderson, A. Beach, and N. Finkelstein, "Facilitating change in undergraduate STEM instructional practices: An analytic review of the literature," *J. Res. Sci. Teach.*, vol. 48, no. 8, pp. 952–984, 2011, doi: 10.1002/tea.20439.
- [8] A. L. Beach and M. D. Cox, "The Impact of Faculty Learning Communities on Teaching and Learning," *Learn. Communities J.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 7–27, 2009.
- [9] S. Pulford, N. Ruzycki, C. J. Finelli, L. Hahn, and D. Thorsen, "Making Value for Faculty : Learning Communities in Engineering Faculty Development," in *122nd ASEE Annual Conference*, 2015, no. 12769.
- [10] S. Schmitz, T. E. Ebersole, C. Morrell, and C. Parker, "Measuring the Effectiveness of Community College Faculty Learning Communities on Student Performance," *Learn. Communities J.*, vol. 10, pp. 87–108, 2018.
- [11] T. Lisagor and A. Lucero-liu, "Using Faculty Learning Communities to Improve Latino Student Success," *Learn. Communities J.*, vol. 5, pp. 73–96, 2013.
- [12] D. Ebert-may, T. L. Derting, J. Hodder, J. L. Momsen, and T. M. Long, "What We Say Is Not What We Do : Effective Evaluation of Faculty Professional Development Programs," no. July, 2011, doi: 10.1525/bio.2011.61.7.9.
- [13] L. Cohen, L. Manion, and K. Morrison, *Research Methods in Education*, 7th ed. Routledge, 2011.
- [14] E. Crawley, J. Malmqvist, S. Ostlund, and D. Brodeur, *Rethinking Engineering Education The CDIO approach*. NY: Springer, 2007.
- [15] C. Erlingsson and P. Brysiewicz, "A hands-on guide to doing content analysis," *African J. Emerg. Med.*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 93–99, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.afjem.2017.08.001.